

Frequency-Domain Approaches for Gaussian Noise Reduction in Astronomical Images: A Quantitative Comparison

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ABSTRACT

Astronomical images are often degraded by Gaussian noise introduced during image acquisition and transmission, which significantly affects the visibility of faint celestial structures. Effective noise reduction is therefore essential for reliable astronomical observation and analysis. This study presents a comparative evaluation of three commonly used denoising techniques Wiener, arithmetic mean, and median filtering within the framework of Fourier-based image restoration. Gaussian noise with fixed statistical parameters was artificially added to multiple astronomical images to ensure fair and controlled testing conditions. Each filtering method was then applied, and the restored images were quantitatively evaluated using four widely accepted image quality metrics: Mean Squared Error (MSE), Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR), Structural Similarity Index (SSIM), and Natural Image Quality Evaluator (NIQE). The experimental results consistently demonstrate that the Wiener filter outperforms the mean and median filters across most evaluation criteria, achieving lower reconstruction error and higher structural similarity while maintaining better perceptual quality. These findings indicate that Wiener filtering in the frequency domain provides a reliable and efficient approach for Gaussian noise reduction in astronomical imaging, offering improved preservation of fine image details critical for scientific interpretation. This work contributes to enhancing practical image restoration strategies for astronomical data analysis.

I INTRODUCTION

Widely used in communications and image processing, the Fourier Transform is one of the most critical applications in science and engineering. In 1822, discovered by Joseph Fourier, the Fourier transform was a discriminatory tool in wave analysis that provided a more genuine representation and understanding of ordinary waves ¹. Whether in a single dimension or across multiple dimensions, the Fourier transform is a tool used to decompose complex periodic wave functions into sinusoidal waves. This decomposition provides an accurate visualization of the wave components in the frequency domain.

From another perspective, the convolution process, a mathematical concept that includes Fourier transform in its operation, is an innovative tool in image filtration and processing. This tool is widely discussed in this paper showing different types of filters that depend on this mathematical operation. One major challenge that faces astronomers is the quality of the captured images from space. Occasionally, some images display undesired distortions, compromising their clarity and causing many issues for astronomers. One distortion that usually appears in astronomical images from space is image noise. This noise usually appears as white opaque dots on random parts of the image, these dots are expressed as random high-frequency pixels. This issue causes a visualization obstacle that makes the image unclear. Therefore, many methods were developed to remove the noise that appears in the images captured for space objects. One innovative method discovered recently is using a filter known as an 'adaptive filter' (AF). This filter is implemented to remove the noise automatically without manipulating the filter's parameters and without any need for adjustment. It recognizes and adapts its own impulse to the resolution of the local signal ². This method effectively removes noises from various images, including astronomical exoplanet images.

This paper comprehensively identifies and analyzes one of the noise distortions that face astronomical images. Section III describes experiments with different filters on astronomical images and estimates the efficient filters to resolve the noise issue found in the images. By comparing three different filters on various astronomical images and reviewing some quantitative data, this paper indicates why these filters are adequate to be used in the astronomical image processing field while treating images from space and which filters are efficient for obtaining higher-quality images.

II MATHEMATICAL BACKGROUND

A. Fourier Transform

One tool primarily used in signal and image processing, the Fourier transform, is widely used for decomposing signal waves. The Fourier transform is a mathematical operation applied to non-periodic and periodic functions to decompose a function into its constitutive frequency components; the Fourier transform transforms and represents the function $f(t)$ from the time (t) domain to the frequency domain $F(v)$ by applying complex mathematical operations to the main function.

$$F(v) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(t) \cdot e^{-2\pi i v t} dt \quad (1)$$

where $f(t)$ represents the function in the time domain, and $F(v)$ represents the Fourier transform of the function with a different input variable v . The term "Transform" is used as a means of transforming the function from the spatial time domain to the frequency domain³. Another essential point to include is the inverse Fourier transform. The inverse transform transforms the function from the frequency domain to the time domain. For instance, this approach can be used when the filters in the Fourier domain are applied, and we want to take the function to its time domain form. The Inverse Fourier transform can be expressed as:

$$f(t) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} F(v) \cdot e^{+2\pi i v t} dv \quad (2)$$

The Approach:

To prove how this complex theorem ended up with form, a small concept related to the Fourier transform called the "Fourier Series" will be discussed. Any simple periodic harmonic wave can be described in terms of trigonometric functions like sines and cosines. For example, if the function $F(t)$ is a periodic function, it can be described as:

$$F(t) = \frac{A_0}{2} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} A_n \cos(2\pi n v_0 t) + B_n \sin(2\pi n v_0 t) \quad (3)$$

where v_0 is the fundamental frequency, n is an integer number to represent the number of the harmonics, the average value of the function over one period is represented as A_0 , and A_n, B_n are coefficients that determine the amplitudes of the cosine and sine terms, respectively, and t is the independent variable. If $F(t)$ is not periodic, all the frequencies must be analyzed as the periodic function. Therefore, the non-periodic function is thought of as a limiting case. As a limiting case of the periodic function, the period tends to infinity, and the fundamental frequency to zero. The summation sign is replaced by an integral sign as the harmonics are more closely spaced, each with amplitude $a(v)$ ³.

These modifications can be written as shown in Eq. (4):

$$F(v) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} a(t) dt \cos(2\pi v t) + \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} b(t) dt \sin(2\pi v t) \quad (4)$$

Equivalently,

$$F(v) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} r(t) \cos(2\pi v t + \Phi(t)) \quad (5)$$

Finally,

$$F(v) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} r(t) \cdot e^{-2\pi i v t} dv \quad (6)$$

where $r(t)$ represents the main function in the time domain. By denoting some variables, the final Fourier transform formula comes up as shown in Eq. (1).

B. Discrete Fourier Transform DFT:

From continuous functions, the discrete Fourier transform, denoted as (DFT), is another approach used in various modern signal and image processing techniques. Instead of a continuous complex function, the DFT is only represented at discrete points on the function. Figure 1 illustrates the difference between the discrete and continuous forms of a function. This discreteness is essential to approximate the original function, so the Fourier transform is computed. Therefore, instead of describing the original function $f(t)$ as a continuous function all over the time domain, the function is described as a finite set of discrete points at equally spaced points⁴. By computing the DFT of a string of points N , an output of delta functions is represented. These delta functions are equally spaced with a coefficient to represent the strength of each delta function⁵. The DFT of a finite periodic function can be expressed as:

$$G(k) = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} g(n) e^{-2\pi i \frac{kn}{N}} \quad (7)$$

where $k = 0, 1, \dots, N-1$. On the time domain, $g(n)$ is only known on N input values $n\Delta t$. On the other hand, $G(k)$ is only known on N output discrete frequencies k/T . Using the inverse DFT, the discrete-time domain signal can be re-obtained from the spectrum of frequencies on the frequency domain⁶. From $G(k)$ function of the available frequencies, the inverse DFT (IDFT) can be expressed as:

$$g(n) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} G(k) e^{2\pi i \frac{kn}{N}} \quad (8)$$

where $n = 0, 1, \dots, N-1$ and the $\frac{1}{N}$ is added as a normalization factor. Computing the inverse Discrete Fourier Transform (IDFT) is a process that preserves all information in a signal. It achieves this by converting the signal's spectrum in the frequency domain back to the original time sequence without any loss of information.

Figure 1: Illustration for the Continuous and Discrete form of a function. (Figure source: A. B. Western, *Fourier Series and Transforms*, unpublished course notes.)

C. Discrete Fourier Transform in 2-D:

In the two-dimensional space, the DFT extension from one dimension to the other is straightforward. The DFT follows the same formula expressed in the one-dimensional space without any manipulation in the main theorem. Defined over a discrete finite 2D grid of size $M \times N$, which is referred to as a simple matrix, the two-dimensional DFT can be expressed as the following:

$$G(k, j) = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} g(n, m) e^{-i2\pi \left(\frac{kn}{N} + \frac{j m}{M} \right)} \quad (9)$$

whereas m and n correspond to the row and column indices of the input matrix, j and k denote the row and column indices of the two-dimensional Fourier transform matrix. Also, $n = 0, 1, \dots, N-1$ and $m = 0, 1, \dots, M-1$. In

order to obtain the original image again, the IDFT (Inverse Discrete Fourier Transform) is computed. Following the same pattern, the two-dimensional IDFT is similar to the one-dimensional case. The IDFT of an image can be expressed as:

$$g(n, m) = \frac{1}{MN} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} g(k, j) e^{+i2\pi(\frac{kn}{N} + \frac{jm}{M})} \quad (10)$$

where $k = 0, 1, \dots, N-1$ and $j = 0, 1, \dots, M-1$. Again as in the one-dimensional case, the normalization factor $\frac{1}{MN}$ is added⁷. The inverse DFT is a crucial section in the image processing field. After treating and filtering an image in the frequency (Fourier) domain, the image is returned to its original form using the inverse DFT operation.

III METHODOLOGY

A. Image Processing Steps

1. Image Representation:

The digital images commonly seen in our daily lives are simply a data matrix, each represented at a discrete point in a row or column. Let $f(m, n)$ be a function that represents discrete coordination on a $M \times N$ matrix, M rows, and N columns. Integer values are used to represent x and y , where $m = 0, 1, 2, \dots, M-1$ and $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N-1$. When an image is sampled, it involves the conversion of a continuous two-dimensional image into a discrete representation by selecting a finite number of sample points from the continuous image. In this process, each element in the matrix $M \times N$ corresponds to a specific element. According to the main function, each of these coordinated elements is referred to as a 'Pixel.' As shown in Eq. (11), the digital image is represented by a matrix that carries pixels each coordinated with the main function.

$$f(m, n) = \begin{bmatrix} f(0, 0) & f(0, 1) & \dots & f(0, N-1) \\ f(1, 0) & f(1, 1) & \dots & f(1, N-1) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ f(M-1, 0) & f(M-1, 1) & \dots & f(M-1, N-1) \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

Each pixel on this matrix carries a value of f that represents the intensity of this pixel. In a simplified image version, there are three equally placed pixel intensity values. As the interval $[0,1]$ is the range of the normalized intensity of each pixel, then each pixel in the image has the value 0, 0.5, or 1. These 3 values are converted to three colors, which are gray, black, or white⁸. Figure 2 shows an Image form and a Matrix form of a digital image.

(a) Normal representation of a digital image

0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0.5	0.5	0.5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0.5	0.5	0.5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0.5	0.5	0.5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.5	0.5	0.5	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.5	0.5	0.5	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.5	0.5	0.5	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

(b) The Matrix representation of a digital image

Figure 2: Illustration of the Matrix and Image form of a digital image

2. Image Noise:

The primary formation of noise in digital images stems from the image acquiring and transmitting processes. When it comes to image acquisition, numerous environmental factors can influence imaging sensors' performance. For instance, using a camera to capture images can cause factors like the level of ambient light and the sensor's temperature to play a significant role in determining the amount of noise present in the final image. On the other hand, during the transmission of images, noise primarily arises from interference encountered within the transmission channel. For example, the images sent via wireless networks can be susceptible to corruption due to external factors such as lightning strikes or other atmospheric disturbances. One noise that commonly appears in images is the Gaussian noise. This noise appears as a random variation in pixel values, with maybe bright or dark pixels scattered throughout the image⁸. The effect of Gaussian noise on a black image is shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Illustration for the Gaussian noise effect on a normal black image

In this study, the Gaussian noise is added to some images during the efficiency evaluation of a filter. This is done to test the ability of a filter to remove noise from images. Mathematically, the Gaussian random variable (noise) can be expressed as:

$$p(z) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma} \cdot e^{-\frac{(z-\bar{z})^2}{2\sigma^2}} \quad -\infty < z < \infty \quad (12)$$

where $p(z)$ represents the noise intensity, \bar{z} is the center value of the position variable z , and σ is the standard deviation. The Gaussian noise is added to three astronomical images during the evaluation. The standard deviation σ and mean were the same in each of the three images to make the evaluation process fair. Variation in these values makes the process of picking up the efficient filter more complicated.

3. Image Restoration:

Image restoration is a process by which a degraded image is rebuilt to restore the original image due to undesired distortions. This image degradation can occur for several reasons, as mentioned in Section III. Due to these distortions, some processing is formed on the images depending on the type or nature of the distortion occurring on the image. The image restoration process's main aim is to minimize the error between the restored image and the original image. Depending on the knowledge of the degradation, the efficiency of the restoration process can be expected.

The image restoration process can be represented as depicted in Figure 4. In this model, $f(m, n)$ represents the input normal image, $h(m, n)$ signifies the degradation function, $\eta(m, n)$ denotes the noise added to the image, $g(m, n)$ stands for the degraded image, and $K(m, n)$ signifies the restored final image. The goal of the restoration process is to minimize the error between the input image $f(m, n)$ and the output restored image $K(m, n)$. The degraded image

$g(m, n)$ enters the filtration process to obtain a higher quality image $K(m, n)$. The degraded image can be expressed mathematically as:

$$g(m, n) = h(m, n) * f(m, n) + \eta(m, n) \quad (13)$$

where $h(m, n)$ represents the degradation function, the symbol $*$ represents the convolution process, and $\eta(m, n)$ is the additive noise. In the filtration stage, the convolution process is an important operation applied to restore the images.⁹

Figure 4: A block diagram shows the image restoration process

The convolution is an operation widely used in image processing that is performed by using another term called the kernel, also known as a window. A kernel is a small matrix of coefficients that is placed on the pixels of the image to compute a new image with new pixels. However, the convolution works by sliding a kernel across the entire image, changing the value of its pixels, which is illustrated in Fig. 5. Each pixel in the image is multiplied by the coefficients that the kernel carries on its pixels. In image processing, the kernels are known as a ‘Convolution matrix’ with its own $M \times N$ size, where M and N are odd integer numbers. Convolution has numerous image-processing applications, including blurring, sharpening, edge detection, and more. The kernel used in the convolution process determines the specific effect obtained. Mathematically, the convolution process with a kernel W of size $m \times n$ and an image $f(x, y)$ can be defined as:

$$w(x, y) * f(x, y) = \sum_{s=-a}^a \sum_{t=-b}^b w(s, t) f(x-s, y-t) \quad (14)$$

where $w(s, t)$ is the kernel with a size of $m \times n$, $a = \frac{(m-1)}{2}$ and $b = \frac{(n-1)}{2}$. The negative sign in Eq. (14) ensures that the coordinates of the functions f and w become aligned when one of them undergoes a 180-degree rotation.

Figure 5: Illustration to show how the kernel is slid over the image (Figure source:Rafael C. Gonzalez, Richard E. Woods. *Digital Image Processing* (Fourth Edition). 330 Hudson Street, New York, NY 10013, (2018).)

B. Filtering Techniques

1. Wiener Filter:

The Wiener filter is a stationary filter designed to restore images degraded by additive noise and blurring. The filter targets to resolve observed random noise in an image assuming known stationary signal and noise spectra. The goal of the Wiener filter is to compute a statistical estimate of an unknown signal using a related signal as an input and filtering that known signal to produce the estimate as an output. Unknown signals are those corrupted by noise, Gaussian noise in this paper, that hits the images randomly. An advantage of the Wiener filter is that it considers minimizing the value of MSE, which is an estimation that a filtered image has higher quality. The Wiener filter is usually applied in the frequency domain. Given that the degraded image is $f(n, m)$, and its Discrete Fourier transform (DFT) is $F(u, v)$. The mathematical process that the Wiener filter depends on can be expressed as:

$$K(u, v) = G(u, v)F(u, v) \quad (15)$$

where $G(u, v)$ is the Wiener filter. The original image spectrum is simply estimated by taking the product of the DFT of the image $F(u, v)$ and the Wiener filter $G(u, v)$. After taking the product, the inverse Fourier transform is applied to return the function again to its image form¹³. The function expressing the Wiener filter can be further simplified to show the operations that the filter depends on during the filtration process, and it is expressed as:

$$G(u, v) = \frac{H^*(u, v)}{|H(u, v)|^2 + K} \quad (16)$$

where $H(u, v)$ is the degradation transfer function (Fourier transform of the spatial degradation)^{6,7}. $H^*(u, v)$ is the complex conjugate of $H(u, v)$, $|H(u, v)|^2 = H^*(u, v)H(u, v)$, and K is a constant added to the terms of $|H(u, v)|^2$. The restored image in the spatial domain is given by the inverse Fourier transform of the frequency domain estimate $K(u, v)$.

2. Arithmetic Mean Filter:

The arithmetic mean filter is another image filter used in the process of denoising images, especially those contaminated with Gaussian noise, that is effective to be applied in the spatial domain. The mean filter depends on the operation of taking the average value of a set of pixels within a local region on the image. The size of this region is mainly the size of the kernel (window) of the applied filter. This process is applied using the kernel and convolution process, discussed in Section III A. Mathematically, The arithmetic mean filter computes the average value of the pixels in the degraded image $f(m, n)$ over the area of the window defined as S_{xy} . Also, S_{xy} represents the set of coordinates in a rectangular window (neighborhood) of size $m \times n$, centered on point (x, y) . The restored image $K(x, y)$ by applying the arithmetic mean filter can be expressed by:

$$K(x, y) = \frac{1}{mn} \sum_{(s,t) \in S_{xy}} f(s, t) \quad (17)$$

In S_{xy} , the pixel's location is represented by its row and column coordinates, denoted by s and t respectively. Applying this filter using a spatial kernel of size $m \times n$ smooths local variations in the image and reduces the random noise contaminating the image.⁸

3. Median Filter:

The median filter is a type of filter that is widely used in the image restoration process. The median filter is one of the most efficient filters in removing various types of noises from the images, including the Gaussian noise. This efficiency is mainly dependent on the method by which this filter performs its operation. The technique that this filter depends on is taking the median of a set of pixels. A kernel of a certain size runs through the image pixel by pixel, replacing each pixel with the median of the intensity levels of neighboring pixels around it. The median filter is considered as a statistic-based filter as it is based on statistical estimations. Mathematically, the restored image $K(x, y)$ using a median filter can be expressed as:

$$K(x, y) = \text{Median}_{(s,t) \in S_{xy}} g(s, t) \quad (18)$$

In the function where S_{xy} constitutes a portion of the image where the filter is utilized, the pixel's position within S_{xy} is denoted by its row and column coordinates, represented as s and t , respectively.

C. Image Quality Assessment Metrics

1. MSE (Mean Square Error):

One of the numerous quantitative image quality assessment metrics, the MSE is the most used estimator in image clarity and quality evaluation. The MSE is based on measuring the error between a pixel in the filtered image and its corresponding pixel in the original image. This comparison estimates how much error appears in the filtered image. From a mathematical-specific perspective, the MSE measures the average of the square of the error difference between the original degraded image and the final filtered image. Therefore, the MSE can be mathematically expressed as:

$$MSE = \frac{1}{MN} \sum_{n=0}^M \sum_{m=1}^N [g(n, m) - f(n, m)]^2 \quad (19)$$

where M and N are the image resolution, $g(n, m)$ represents the output image, and $f(n, m)$ represents the input image. As expressed in Eq. (19), it is observed that the MSE is a measurement of an absolute error between two images, the input original image and the output filtered one. A good indicator that the quality of the output image is outstanding compared to the input one is the approach of the MSE value to zero. ^{10,11}

2. PSNR (Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio):

The PSNR calculates the ratio between the maximum possible signal power and the power of the distorting noise. The usage of the PSNR quality assessment metric is common in the image processing field to measure the quality of reconstruction of degraded image compression codecs. Because many signals have a wide dynamic range, the PSNR is calculated as a logarithmic quantity using the decibel scale. To calculate the PSNR, the signal is considered as the original data, and the noise introduced to it is the error yielded by the distortion. The formula used to calculate the PSNR depends on the MSE value between the input and output images. The PSNR is expressed as:

$$PSNR = \frac{10 \log_{10}(S^2)}{MS} \quad (20)$$

where S is the maximum peak value in the image that can be calculated using the formula:

$$S = 2^B - 1 \quad (21)$$

where B expresses the number of bits per sample; for example, S for an 8-bit grey-scale image is 255. The PSNR is measured in dB as a representation of an absolute error between the pixels of input and output images. A higher value of PSNR indicates the image has a higher quality and vice versa ^{9,11}.

3. SSIM (Structure Similarity Index Method):

Another image assessment metric is the SSIM. This metric measures the similarity between the original and filtered images. To calculate the SSIM, the degradation occurring to an image is considered the change in the structural information between the input and output images. The term structural information illustrates strongly inter-dependent or spatially closed pixels that refer to crucial information in the image domain. The SSIM calculation considers other essential factors for the comparing process; for instance, luminance and contrast masking are considered perceptions during the measurement. Luminance masking refers to the process of making the distortion part of an image less noticeable at the image's edges. Contrast masking, on the other hand, refers to the process of making distortions in an image's texture less obvious. The SSIM can be expressed as:

$$SSIM(x, y) = [l(x, y)]^\alpha \cdot [c(x, y)]^\beta \cdot [s(x, y)]^\gamma \quad (22)$$

where l is the luminance (to compare the brightness), c is the contrast (to differ the bright and dark regions), and s is the structure. α , β , and γ are positive constants ⁹. By further simplification and substitution, Eq. (22) can be expressed as:

$$SSIM(x, y) = \frac{(2\mu_x\mu_y + C_1)(2\sigma_x\sigma_y + C_2)}{(\mu_x^2 + \mu_y^2 + C_3)(\sigma_x^2 + \sigma_y^2 + C_4)} \quad (23)$$

where μ_x and μ_y are the local means, σ_x and σ_y are the standard deviations, and C_1 and C_2 are Constant values used to avoid zero denominators. The approach of the SSIM value to 1 indicates a higher image quality ¹¹.

4. NIQE (Natural Image Quality Evaluator):

The NIQE is a no-reference image quality assessment method that calculates an image's quality score. It compares the image to a default model computed from images of natural scenes. A smaller score indicates better perceptual quality.

The mathematical calculations for NIQE involve several steps. First, the image is preprocessed to remove color information and normalize the intensity values. Then, the image is divided into non-overlapping blocks, and statistical features are extracted from each block. These features include measures of sharpness, contrast, and texture. Next, the extracted features are compared to a default model computed from images of natural scenes. This model represents the distribution of feature values typically observed in natural images. The comparison uses a statistical distance measure, such as the Mahalanobis distance. Finally, the NIQE score for the image is computed as the average distance between the extracted features and the default model. A smaller score indicates that the image is more similar to natural scenes and therefore has better perceptual quality¹².

IV RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The evaluation process takes several steps to precisely evaluate the three chosen filters, from the image selection to the assessment metrics comparison. The images included are randomly selected. The main theme for the images is astronomical space images. The images of galaxies, nebulae, and the black dominant black backgrounds are mostly appropriate selections for testing the efficiency of the filters. The noise appearing in these images is the main aspect considered as the comparison factor between the filters. Therefore, the same Gaussian noise is added to the images to make the testing process comprehensively fair. Adding Gaussian noise gives a perception of an image of random white dots appearing on various regions. After adding the Gaussian noise, the selected three filters, Wiener filter, Mean filter, and Median filter, are performed on the images. Each filter is applied to the three images, Space A, Space B, and Space C, as shown in Fig. 6, producing nine different combinations of filtered astronomical images. To evaluate these combinations, four quality assessment metrics are included to determine which filter is the most effective in denoising the astronomical images, discussed in Section III. Finally, instead of having numerous scattered data without organization, the data obtained from this evaluation process is formally listed in tables to compare the images in a well-oriented way.

Figure 6: The three images included during the evaluation process of the filters. (Figure source: (Hubble Home. (n.d.). <https://hubblesite.org/>)

The experiments were conducted on a software program used for calculating purposes by engineers. The software program is called 'MATLAB'. As a result of these experiments, Tables 1,2, and 3 were obtained to show the results of applying each filter on the three images, as shown in Fig. 6, illustrating the values of the assessment metrics. The experiments were conducted on a software program used for calculating purposes by engineers. The software program is called 'MATLAB'.

Table 1: The MSE, PSNR, SSIM, and NIQE scores resulting from the application of the Wiener filter to three selected degraded astronomical images are presented. These images were subjected to Gaussian noise for degradation.

Wiener Filter			
Metrics	Space A.	Space B.	Space C.
MSE	172.85	172.69	179.61
PSNR	25.85	25.76	25.59
SSIM	0.5879	0.7418	0.6002
NIQE Score	4.7914	3.9415	5.3171

Table 2: The MSE, PSNR, SSIM, and NIQE scores resulting from the application of the Arithmetic Mean filter to three selected degraded astronomical images are presented. These images were subjected to Gaussian noise for degradation.

Arithmetic Mean Filter			
Metrics	Space A.	Space B.	Space C.
MSE	175.69	184.70	182.04
PSNR	25.68	25.47	25.53
SSIM	0.5719	0.7123	0.5944
NIQE Score	4.5082	5.2267	4.9715

Table 3: The MSE, PSNR, SSIM, and NIQE scores resulting from the application of the Median filter to three selected degraded astronomical images are presented. These images were subjected to Gaussian noise for degradation.

Median Filter			
Metrics	Space A.	Space B.	Space C.
MSE	178.29	182.25	184.80
PSNR	25.62	25.45	25.46
SSIM	0.5496	0.6832	0.5710
NIQE Score	3.5889	3.7531	3.9581

From Table 1 to Table 3, it can be observed that the efficiency of the Wiener filter is the best among the 3 filters. From Table 2 and Table 3, it can be observed that the Arithmetic Mean filter is more efficient than the Median filter. From Table 1, it is observed that the lowest MSE value that the Wiener filter reached was 172.61 in (Space. C), which is the lowest between the two other filters, Table. 2 and Table. 3. The filtration process computed on the three noised images using Wiener Filter can be observed by comparing Fig. 7 and Fig. 8.

Figure 7: The three astronomical images after adding the Gaussian noise, but before computing the Wiener filter

Figure 8: The three astronomical images results after computing the Wiener Filter

For the two other filters, the lowest MSE value for the Mean filter was 175.69 in (Space. A) and 178.29 in (Space. A) for the Median filter, and this is an indicator that the Wiener filter works better. For the PSNR value, it observed from Table 1 that the highest value, which is 25.85, was also performed by the Wiener filter in (Space. A). The Arithmetic Mean filter scored the highest value of 25.68 in (Space. A), and the Median filter scored the highest value of 25.62 in (Space. A). The Wiener filter also scored the highest SSIM value of 0.7418 in (Space. B), while the highest value score by the Mean and Median filters is 0.7123 in (Space. B) and 0.6832 in (Space. B), respectively. Finally, the NIQE scores were higher in the images restored by the Wiener filter. The highest score observed by the Wiener filter was 5.3171 in (Space C.), while the observed highest scores in the Mean and Median filters were 5.2267 in (Space B.) and 3.9581 in (Space C.), respectively.

V SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

This paper discusses the application of the Fourier Transform in image restoration. Fourier Transform has been shown to be an effective tool for analyzing non-stationary signals in the frequency domain. The Discrete Fourier Transform DFT transforms the images and finds the frequency spectrum during the restoration process. Image restoration techniques such as the Wiener filter, Arithmetic Mean filter, and Median filter are implemented using the Fourier Transform as the primary tool. Experiments were conducted by introducing Gaussian noise to degrade the images and create noisy versions. The outcomes of these experiments, conducted on the selected image collection, reveal that the Wiener filter method surpasses the performance of the other two methods. Metrics such as MSE, PSNR, SSIM, and NIQE scores were used for comparison. Enhancing the quality of image restoration is achievable through the development of novel algorithms that harness the potential of Fourier Transform (FT) and by integrating FT with various mathematical techniques.

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VII REFERENCES

- ^[1] Debnath, L. *A short biography of Joseph Fourier and historical development of Fourier series and Fourier transforms. International Journal of Mathematical Education in Science and Technology*, (2011).
- ^[2] Lorenz, H., Richter, G. M., Capaccioli, M., Longo, G. *Adaptive Filtering in Astronomical Image Processing - Part One - Basic Considerations and Examples. Astronomy and Astrophysics*, **277**, (1993).

- ^[3]James, J. F. *A Student's Guide to Fourier Transforms with Applications in Physics and Engineering* (3rd ed.). (2011).
- ^[4] Baddour. *Discrete two-dimensional Fourier transform in polar coordinates part I: Theory and operational rules. Mathematics*, **7(8)**, (2019).
- ^[5] Bracewell, R. N. *The Fourier Transform and Its Applications* (3rd ed.). (2000).
- ^[6] John, A. M., Khanna, K., Prasad, R. R., Pillai, L. G. *A review on the application of Fourier transform in image restoration. 2020 Fourth International Conference on I-SMAC (IoT in Social, Mobile, Analytics and Cloud) (I-SMAC)*, (2020).
- ^[7] Rao, K.R., Kim, D.N., Hwang, J.J. *Fast Fourier Transform: Algorithms and Applications*. Springer, Dordrecht Heidelberg London New York, (2010).
- ^[8] Rafael C. Gonzalez, Richard E. Woods. *Digital Image Processing* (Fourth Edition). 330 Hudson Street, New York, NY 10013, (2018).
- ^[9] Setiadi, D. R. *PSNR vs SSIM: Imperceptibility Quality Assessment for Image Steganography. Multimedia Tools and Applications*, **80(6)**, (2020).
- ^[10] J.K. Mandal, Suresh Chandra Satapathy, Manas Kumar Sanyal, Partha Pratim Sarkar, Anirban Mukhopadhyay. *Information Systems Design and Intelligent Applications: Proceedings of Second International Conference, Volume 1*, (2015).
- ^[11] U. Sara, M. Akter, M. S. Uddin. *Image Quality Assessment through FSIM, SSIM, MSE and PSNR—A Comparative Study. Journal of Computer and Communications*, **07(03)** (2019).
- ^[12] A. Zvezdakova, D. Kulikov, D. Kondranin, D. Vatolin. *Barriers towards no-reference metrics application to compressed video quality analysis: On the example of no-reference metric NIQE. GraphiCon'2019 Proceedings. Volume 2*, (2019).
- ^[13] J. Yoo, C. W. Ahn. *Image restoration by blind-Wiener filter. IET Image Processing*, **8(12)**, (2014).